

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND BLOCKCHAIN IN HEALTHCARE

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Abstract

The article is devoted to increasing the efficiency of blockchain technology and artificial intelligence in the field of health care in their combination. The problem of a high number of medical errors and the possibility of informatization of the health sector is put. Examples of advantages and weaknesses of both technologies are given. It is proved that the combination of artificial intelligence and blockchain can improve the security of big data, make decisions made by artificial intelligence more transparent, explainable and trustworthy, to reduce the number of medical errors, to make a step towards individualized medicine.

Keywords: healthcare, blockchain, artificial intelligence, their combination.

The volume of medical knowledge in the world is increasing exponentially: a new medical article appears every 20 minutes. But the physician's ability to track the necessary information, to comprehend it and to apply it in practice is limited. In Europe alone, every tenth patient encounters medical errors annually. In the United States, about 100,000 patients die each year from misdiagnoses, and deaths from medical errors are the fifth leading cause of death. Globally, the discrepancy between postmortem and vital diagnoses is 20-25%, that is, every fourth death occurs from a disease that was not detected during life by doctors [4].

Artificial intelligence is able to reduce the risk of errors in diagnosis and treatment by about 70%, because it has the full amount of medical information. Artificial intelligence is capable of processing thousands of pages of text per second to find the necessary information, which no doctor can do.

Examples of the use of artificial intelligence include recognition of MRI scans, ultrasound scans, cardiograms, development of drugs with preset properties; design of comfortable prostheses taking into account individual anatomical features of the person; analysis of the clinical picture of the patient's condition and assistance in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer; determination of risk groups, development of treatment options, and so on. The World Health Organization has developed an application in the smartphone mHealth based on artificial intelligence for preventive purposes. With its help, everyone can assess their health status, get acquainted with a preliminary diagnosis and find out which doctors they should consult. There is a mobile application (Sense.ly) with a rehabilitation focus, for those who are discharged from clinics. Artificial intelligence makes it possible to decipher genetic analysis data (Sophia Genetics app) and diagnose genetic diseases. The DermaCompare app can identify melanoma moles on the skin. Artificial intelligence selects drugs not only according to the disease, but also according to the individual's personality (MedClueRx) [2,3,9,10,14].

There are many such examples. Artificial intelligence technologies in health care are developing rapidly. A new area of their application is the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health - ICF - developed and published by the World Health Organization [6]. It was developed not to describe nosologies and diagnose a person, but to measure an individual's state of health (body functions and structure), including social environmental factors that affect health. According to the ICF, assessing the state of functioning of an individual as a biological and social being requires the participation of different specialists, that is, an interdisciplinary approach (psychological, psychophysiological, neuropsychological, pedagogical, physiological, medical), that is, working with big data. But there are problems associated with the storage of such data, their invariability, persuasiveness of interpretation, preservation of personal privacy rights. Blockchain technology could help solve these problems in processing big data [3].

Blockchain is an open, distributed registry of records that form a chain, shared by agreement by all users in the network. One of the advantages of blockchain is that it is virtually impossible to change information without the consent of the entire network. Blockchain is now seen as the basis for creating a serverless Internet, a decentralized World Wide Web in which users have control over their personal data. However, blockchain also has weaknesses related to scalability and efficiency issues [2,3].

Combining artificial intelligence and blockchain technologies gives rise to the possibility of their mutual complementarity and optimization. In this tandem, blockchain secures big data, allows people to control their data, explains the decision-making steps of artificial intelligence, makes them transparent decisions, explainable and trustworthy [7].

In doing so, artificial intelligence enhances its security, personalization and control, and provides protection against tampering. It helps to facilitate decision making, promotes automation and blockchain optimization for higher performance and better control, get-

ting away from the implicit stages of the decision-making procedure. Artificial intelligence can help blockchain improve the performance of mining algorithms, reduce blockchain size, and improve data storage management. Such an alliance helps to increase the field of application of artificial intelligence and the trust in it [1,2,3].

Doctors and science will have access to a huge amount of anonymous medical data. The search for drugs will be accelerated. Care for people with rare diseases will increase. Increased confidence in patients that they will not be compromised and their personal data will not be hacked by intruders.

Medical professionals will have the rationale for decisions that are given by machine intelligence ("black boxes"), will be able to review logs describing the decision-making process. This is important when investigating incidents [5,8].

Many experts believe that the future of blockchain and artificial intelligence are interconnected. Their synergy will be one of the most significant in the coming decades, because only in tandem will these two technologies be able to realize their full potential: reliable unchanged data storage (that is, verifiability) and transparency of decisions, which will increase trust in them [13].

Decentralized blockchain can facilitate the development of decentralized artificial intelligence. Sharing a huge amount of computing resources is more productive than individual supercomputers. Decentralized management of medical data, where all stakeholders can control access to the same medical records, patient charts, patient histories and predictive treatment programs while being completely incognito about who owns them, will improve the quality of medical diagnoses and reduce medical errors. It will increase evidence-based relationships between methods of prevention, treatment and rehabilitation; between treatment protocols, patient monitoring and the results obtained [2,3].

Transition to ultra-precise, individualized medicine will be possible, taking into account genetic and other characteristics of the patient, taking into account lifestyle, quality of the environment, social and economic status of the person. Such possibilities will increase the effectiveness of diagnosis and treatment of coronavirus infection [11,12].

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